

Membrane Electrode Assembly (MEA) CO₂ Electrolyzer Model – Guide

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This document serves as a short explanation regarding the two base case models for a i) Full MEA configuration and an ii) Exchange MEA configuration. Both models are built on the same framework, and largely follow the same modeling approach, but some crucial differences remain. Variations on these base case models have been used to generate the result of the paper *Heating Dictates the Scalability of CO₂ Electrolyzer Types*, Hurkmans et al. Therefore, basically all the argumentation and assumptions can be found in that paper.

Here are some key aspects to keep in mind when you want to use these models:

- Both models are based on the work by Weng et al, specifically: *Towards membrane-electrode assembly systems for CO₂ reduction: a modeling study* (<https://pubs.rsc.org/en/content/articlehtml/2019/ee/c9ee00909d>). This model was developed in 1D, the main difference is the expansion to 2 dimensions which allows for better control of boundary conditions, and if done properly, allows for the modeling of down-the-channel effects.
- Due to the high degree of coupling between governing equations, the models are highly non-linear and difficult to solve numerically. As a result, the modelling domain in the flow direction is small. It can be attempted to increase this streamwise direction, but I strongly recommend to relax the non-linearity in that case. This can be done by:
 - o Not solving for the temperature distribution (i.e. assuming isothermal operation, which is in my opinion fine for the exchange MEA model as our results indicate minor heating)
 - o (Partially) Decoupling the ionic conductivity from the mass transport within the electrolyte and membrane. This can easily be done by for instance assuming a constant ionic conductivity based on literature values (i.e. going from tertiary current distribution to secondary current distribution), or by averaging the ionic content of a part of the ionomer domain. An example of the latter approach can be found in Blake et al, *Inhomogeneities in the Catholyte Channel Limit the Upscaling of CO₂ Flow Electrolysers* (<https://pubs.acs.org/doi/full/10.1021/acssuschemeng.2c06129>)
 - o Not solving for dissolved species concentrations. Depending on your desired modeling goal, this can be fine, and will make modeling significantly faster and more robust.
- If 2D effects are unimportant, I would consider building the model in 1D. This will make the model much faster and more robust to varying parameters. The main difficulty here is to think about what boundary conditions make sense. I suggest taking a look at Weng's base case model.
- Both base case models allow for variation in parameters, for instance: varying the operating temperature, dimensions, flowrates etc. Be advised that this may hinder convergence in certain cases.
- In case of difficulty in convergence; meshing, initial conditions, and the solver procedure are crucial. For meshing, I advise to investigate the results you are solving for, more often than not you will find that, for instance, your concentrations exhibit oscillations near a boundary, which is an obvious sign to increase your mesh refinement locally. Initial conditions are crucial in enforcing convergence even at low applied potentials, make sure that your system is in equilibrium by employing smart initial conditions. Choosing the right solver may also be important. COMSOL has plenty of blog posts wherein they explain how these solvers operate, and which solvers are right for the job.

Below, specific aspects of both models are discussed.

Exchange MEA (“Exchange_MEA_base_case_solved.mph”)

- In the exchange MEA configuration, a Donnan potential exists at the interface between the membrane and the electrolyte solution. In the catalyst layers, ionomer is present. Assuming proper contact, there should not be a potential jump over the interface of the catalyst layer and the membrane. However, due to restrictions in COMSOL, it is not possible to enforce this very easily. As a work around, the electroneutrality definition in the cathode catalyst is manually changed in the *equation view* of COMSOL. For an explanation on using of the equation view: (<https://www.comsol.com/support/learning-center/article/Viewing-and-Accessing-the-Equations-and-Variables-for-Physics-Feature-Nodes-30761/122>)
- In the model, the water content in the membrane phase is modelled through the water activity which is achieved by introducing a custom transport equation with *Coefficient form PDE*. Alternatively, one can approach the transport of water simply as a dissolved species (as done by Weng et al).
- This particular model has been solved with somewhat loosened strictness on mesh settings, that way it is easier and faster to converge. As a result, there may be some minor local errors in dissolved species concentrations as the homogeneous reaction rates will tend to oscillate.

Full MEA (“Full_MEA_base_case_solved.mph”)

- The tertiary current distribution model cannot be used for this configuration, as the electroneutrality constraint imposes negative concentrations of K^+ . I work around this issue by adding an additional (artificial) term in the Nernst-Planck equation which prevents charge separation (i.e. maintains electroneutrality) while also ensuring physically sound concentrations. The manner in which this is done is discussed in detail in the supplementary information of the corresponding paper.
- Instead of a stationary solver, a transient solver is employed to achieve convergence (this is preferred due to the use of the artificial charge separation limiter). This is done by ramping the applied potential with a smoothed step function. A certain potential is held for a certain amount of time wherein a steady state is reached. As such, when observing results, make sure you analyze the data that is in the steady state regime.